

CHARACTERISTICS OF CREATING AN EVENTS SCENARIO

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about reforms in the fields of art, culture, and music in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the order of script writing, types of scripts, cultural events, and the organization of cultural events.

Keywords: script, types of script, movie script, circus script, television script, public cultural event script, radio script.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере искусства, культуры и музыки в Республике Узбекистан, порядке написания сценариев, видах сценариев, культурно-массовых мероприятиях, организации культурно-массовых мероприятий.

Ключевые слова: сценарий, виды сценария, киносценарий, цирковой сценарий, телевизионный сценарий, сценарий культурно-массового мероприятия, радиосценарий.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi san'at, madaniyat, musiqa kabi sohalardagi islohotlar, senariy yozish tartibi, senariy turlari, madaniy tadbirlar, madaniy tadbirlarni tashkil etish haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: senariy, senariy turlari, kino senariy, sirk senariysi, televizion senariy, ommaviy madaniy tadbir senariysi, radio senariysi.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, in May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2], 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts

appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

Scenarios are divided into a number of types depending on the types of cultural and educational events and the purpose of the activity, and each of them has its own characteristics. If we analyze the term “Scenario” at this point, the word “Scenario” is derived from the Italian word, according to U. Karaboyev in his book “Artistic and public events”, which means “the plan, scheme of the work”. In the dictionaries, the scenario:

- 1) screenplay;
- 2) the plan of the dramatic work performed in the theater, the plot line, the description of the dramatic movement in the opera, in the ballet - the perfect description of the subject including all the dances and mimes;
- 3) it is explained that the time and order of the participants in the play are shown in the 1st guide.

Khaidar Muhammad writes in his book “The Mask of Screenwriting” that “Screenwriting” is derived from the Persian word “Navosanda” meaning “writer” and “writer”, and the term “Screenwriting” was created and introduced. In this book, the author has provided valuable information on the scenario of television, film and theatrical performances. In other sources – “Scenario” (in Italian “Scenario” means a literary-dramatic work), is a literary description of the content of the event, in which, based on a serious sequence, the theme and idea, which are the elements of action, as it is written that transition from fragment to binary, blocks, decorations, texts are fully displayed. But in any case, it is appropriate to describe that the scenario is a complete written description of the events, celebrations and performances. The following tasks are performed during script writing:

- the venue of the event is studied;
- the idea of the topic and event originated from the local conditions resources are sought without;
- documentary materials are artisticized;
- ways of using stage techniques are sought, effective means are selected.

Associate professor V. Rustamov, a specialist in the organization of public cultural events, said that directing has many specialties (for example, theater directing, television directing, radio directing, puppet theater directing, public holidays and performances (such as directing, etc.) The screenplay is also divided into several types according to their different specialties and nature. For example:

1. Movie screenplay - (screenplay of feature films, screenplay of documentary films, screenplay of popular scientific films, screenplay of puppet and animated films). This is one of the unique fields, it is a work that is carried out in a combination of creative and organizational work that requires great skill. Not all screenwriters write KinoSenary. In the film scenario, the realities in the frame, the place to be filmed, various noises, sounds and voices, the actor's position, actions, various conflicts, in a word, all the artistic elements that serve for the success of the film (cinema). creative, technical processes are reflected in the written statement.

The creation of Cinematography itself is based on the characteristics of several types. For example, there are differences and similarities between making a feature film and making a documentary film. In feature films, the director interprets the texture image, improvisation or performance as he wishes. In documentaries, work is carried out within the framework of specific objects and subjects. It is necessary to make the given facts clear and concise without changing them.

2. Television scenarios - (scripts of literary-artistic programs, publicistic - news programs, scripts of spiritual-educational programs, scripts of socio-political programs, entertainment entertainment shows Script, television movies Script, musical shows Script, etc.). If the film is created on the basis of a single scenario taken separately, in the process of filming in the desired place, in the necessary objects, television scenarios are mainly considered from the point of view of programs on different topics.

This process is carried out in the form of various conversations, interviews, meetings, and dialogues, and when making a film, filming can be done at any time depending on the director's proposal and the actors' time. The exact text of the script must be included in the creation of the film. There will be many opportunities to make changes and additions in the process of filming it. However, we do not think that it is necessary to have a full, perfectly written script when preparing shows. For example, when it is necessary to organize a meeting with a father who has reached the age of 100 and to film it, the presenter asks various questions prepared by the editor or the author of the program, and the father answers them, and the presenter can end the show by giving a conclusion.

3. Broadcasting scenario - (social-political broadcasting scenario, literary-artistic broadcasting scenario, journalistic-informational broadcasting scenario, musical broadcasting scenario, spiritual-educational broadcasting scenario,

entertainment broadcasting scenario, etc.) - mainly the text plays a big role in this. It is important to know how to create a scenario when developing a mix of different concert programs and broadcasts on different topics that will appeal to listeners and meet their interests. In radio broadcasting, ready-made information can be freely used based on the assignment given by the editor.

4. Scenario of circus shows - (consists of a sequence of different sports shows, acrobats, animal performances, clown and solo numbers, gatekeeper, etc. numbers).

It is also necessary to create a scenario for circus performances. Because the sequence of performances, a scenario is needed to prepare for the next numbers. The program is often used in such shows. Preparation and demonstration will be carried out according to the program. The person who prepared the number is responsible for the work performed in each individual number.

5. Scenarios of public events and shows - (public theatrical performances, theatrical concerts, literary-artistic, literary-musical compositions, ceremonial performances, public sports performances, performances on water and ice, carnival, folk performances, art-publicistic compositions etc. Scenarios are included). Organization of public holidays, theatrical performances is a field that needs to be studied separately. The notions of public holidays in Uzbekistan are directly related to director B. Saifullaev's work at the Tashkent State Institute of Culture in the 1980s and 1990s after he went to study in Leningrad. The director, who deeply understood the need for a separate school to organize public events and performances, managed to carry out a lot of scientific and practical work on the development of this field. An example of this is field performances on various topics in those times. It should be noted that the Uzbek folk, classical songs and hymns are based on folklore or texts related to classical poetry. Poetic works created by representatives of classical literature are highly valued by our people as examples of high creativity.[4]

The peculiarity of the organization of public events and performances is that they are held in non-standard, non-standard spaces, and there should be a "stage in a box" in it. It is not difficult to understand that it is an area that requires a serious approach, which is characterized by the lack of equipment, the lack of special skills of its participants, the large number of participants and other aspects. The most difficult aspect is the absence of a ready-made dramatic source, as in the case of staging a play. When writing a script for events held on the fields, it is a process that requires a special skill for the screenwriter to

correctly understand the director's opinion, his point of view, and to fully use the tools that give meaning to the field.

Currently, scenarios are being written for the organization of scientific conferences. An example of this is the lectures held at the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan. Such events are called scientific and educational events.

A vivid example of this is the program prepared for the video selector (conference) on the topic "Reading culture" held by professors and teachers of Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan for all higher education institutions. For such events, the scenario is not completely written, but the scenario program is prepared. (Lectures and other materials within the program are submitted based on the required forms). Any program should be short and concise, covering all aspects of the process. The art of cinema is an important tool in shaping the audience's perception, vision and aesthetic taste of reality.[5]

Another one of the scientific conferences are lectures. Lectures are held in the form of lectures and opinions of scientists on a specific topic. Lectorium - (Krt. lectorium, German: Lettner) - a high wooden pulpit placed during worship in ancient Catholic churches. Lectures appeared in Italy in the 11th century, and later in Germany and France. Currently, lectures are more related to scientific events, where scientific opinions are exchanged based on a certain topic. Such activities have a great impact on increasing the scientific potential of people, expanding their worldviews, and increasing their knowledge. Being clear about the types and genres of events makes it easier to create a scenario. Because the screenwriter does not get distracted when working on a specific genre, he follows a clear, straight path. It is worth mentioning that each event has its own procedure (procedure, work steps, requirements) that requires a unique approach. Its dramatic basis, and these features and requirements must be taken into account when creating a scenario. In conclusion, it can be said that the program of each event should be prepared in a way that is thorough, clear and understandable to everyone.

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